

Handwashing practices and associated factors among medical doctors at a tertiary hospital in northern Nigeria: implications for infection prevention and control

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Abstract

Background: Hospital-acquired infections (HAIs) pose a significant threat to patient safety, particularly in low- and middle-income countries. Hand hygiene is the most effective measure for preventing HAIs, yet compliance among healthcare workers, including medical doctors, is often suboptimal. This study assessed handwashing practices and associated factors among medical doctors in a major tertiary hospital in Northern Nigeria. **Materials and Methods:** A hospital-based cross-sectional study was conducted among 74 medical doctors in selected medical and surgical departments of Ahmadu Bello University Teaching Hospital (ABUTH), Zaria, from December 2019 to February 2020. Participants were selected using simple random sampling. Data were collected using a semi-structured, self-administered questionnaire adapted from the WHO "My Five Moments for Hand Hygiene" tool. Handwashing practice was scored and categorised as good ($\geq 67\%$), fair (34-66%), or poor ($\leq 33\%$). Data were analysed using SPSS version 26. Bivariate and multivariable logistic regression analyses were employed to identify predictors of good handwashing practice, with significance set at $p < 0.05$. **Results:** The response rate was 92.5% (74/80). The mean age of participants was 36.1 ± 8.4 years, and 79.7% were male. Overall, 67.6% demonstrated good handwashing practice. While 60% had received formal hand hygiene training, significant gaps in practice were noted, particularly before patient contact. Surgeons were 2.5 times more likely to have good handwashing practice compared to physicians (adjusted odds ratio [aOR] = 2.51; 95% CI: 1.01-6.25; $p=0.048$). Major barriers to optimal hand hygiene included lack of running water (81.7%), lack of soap (60.8%), and high patient load (60.8%). **Conclusions:** Although a majority of medical doctors demonstrated good handwashing practice, a substantial proportion did not, and compliance with specific indications was inconsistent. Infrastructural deficiencies and workload were major barriers. Targeted interventions, including ensuring the consistent availability of hand hygiene resources and sustained training, are crucial for improving compliance and reducing HAIs.

Keywords: Hand hygiene, Hand washing, Hospital-acquired infections, Infection control, Medical doctors, Nigeria

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Introduction

Hospital-acquired infections (HAIs), also known as healthcare-associated infections, are infections that patients acquire while receiving treatment for other conditions within a healthcare setting. They are defined as infections that occur 48 hours or more after admission or within 30 days of discharge.¹ HAIs represent a major global patient safety challenge, leading to prolonged hospital stays, increased morbidity and mortality, and substantial additional healthcare costs.² The burden is disproportionately high in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs), where infection prevention and control (IPC) practices and infrastructure are often inadequate.³

Hand hygiene is universally recognised as the single most effective and cost-efficient intervention to prevent the transmission of pathogens in healthcare settings.⁴ This principle, first demonstrated by Semmelweis in the 19th century, has been repeatedly validated and forms the cornerstone of modern IPC strategies, as outlined in the World Health Organisation (WHO) "My Five Moments for Hand Hygiene" guidelines.^{5,6} Despite robust evidence and global campaigns, compliance with hand hygiene among healthcare workers (HCWs) remains poor worldwide, with average compliance often below 50% in many settings, including Nigeria.^{7,8} Medical doctors, in particular, play a critical role. Their hand hygiene practices directly impact patient outcomes, and they serve as role models for other HCWs, influencing the overall safety culture.⁹ Understanding the specific barriers and facilitators for this group is essential for designing effective interventions.

In Nigeria, studies have identified multiple factors contributing to poor hand hygiene, including inadequate water supply and sanitation facilities, lack of alcohol-based hand rubs, high patient-to-staff ratios, and insufficient institutional enforcement.^{10,11} However, data specifically focusing on medical doctors in tertiary hospitals in Northern Nigeria remain limited. This study aimed to assess handwashing practices, identify associated sociodemographic factors, and explore perceived barriers among medical doctors at Ahmadu Bello University Teaching Hospital (ABUTH), Zaria, to provide evidence to inform targeted IPC improvements.

Materials and Methods

Study Design and Setting

This was a hospital-based cross-sectional study conducted over three months, from December 2019 to February 2020. The study was conducted at Ahmadu Bello University Teaching Hospital (ABUTH), Shika, Zaria, a major tertiary health facility in Kaduna State, North-Western Nigeria. ABUTH provides specialised medical services and serves as a major referral centre for the region.

Study Population

The study population comprised medical doctors who were directly involved in patient care and had been working for at least six months in the selected clinical departments. Doctors on leave during the data collection period or those not in clinical roles (e.g., administrative, research-only) were excluded.

Sample Size and Sampling Technique

A multi-step approach was used to determine the sample size.

- **Step 1 (Initial Sample Size):** Using the formula for a single proportion in a cross-sectional study, $n_0 = Z^2 pq/d^2$. With a 95% confidence level ($Z=1.96$), a precision (d) of 5%, and taking the prevalence (p) of good hand hygiene practice as 63% from a WHO multimodal strategy study by Moro et al. [12], $q = 1-p = 0.37$. The calculation yielded $n_0 = (1.96^2 * 0.63 * 0.37)/0.05^2 = 358$.
- **Step 2 (Adjusting for Non-Response):** To account for a potential 10% non-response rate, the sample size was adjusted to $n_1 = 358/0.9 = 398$.
- **Step 3 (Finite Population Correction):** As the total number of eligible medical doctors in the two selected clinical departments was estimated at 100 ($N < 10,000$), a finite population correction was applied using the formula: $n_f = n_1/(1 + (n_1 - 1)/N)$. This resulted in a final target sample size of 80.

Two clinical departments (Internal Medicine (representing physicians) and General Surgery (representing surgeons) were purposively selected from the five major departments providing direct patient care. A sampling frame of eligible doctors was obtained from each department. From these, 40 doctors per department were selected using simple random sampling (by balloting) to achieve the target sample size.

Data Collection Instrument and Procedure

Data were collected using a semi-structured, self-administered questionnaire. The questionnaire was developed by adapting questions from the WHO "My Five Moments for Hand Hygiene" tool and a review of relevant literature.^{5,13} It consisted of four sections:

1. **Socio-demographic characteristics:** Age, sex, marital status, speciality, and years of professional experience.
2. **Handwashing practices:** Frequency and timing of handwashing based on the WHO Five Moments (e.g., before patient contact, after patient contact, before aseptic task).
3. **Barriers to hand hygiene:** A list of potential challenges (e.g., lack of water, lack of soap, high workload) for respondents to select.
4. **Perception of HAIs:** Respondents' views on the prevalence of HAIs in the hospital.

The questionnaire was pretested among 8 medical doctors (10% of the sample size) at Barau Dikko

Teaching Hospital, Kaduna, to assess clarity, comprehensibility, and flow. The Cronbach's alpha coefficient for the pretested instrument was 0.73, indicating acceptable internal consistency. Completed questionnaires were collected by the researchers after 48-72 hours to ensure anonymity and encourage participation.

Data Analysis

Data were entered, cleaned, and analysed using IBM SPSS Statistics for Windows, Version 26.0 (IBM Corp., Armonk, N.Y., USA). Categorical variables were summarised as frequencies and percentages. Continuous variables were assessed for normality; age was presented as mean \pm standard deviation (SD), while duration of service, which was not normally distributed, was presented as median with interquartile range (IQR).

Measurement of Handwashing Practice:

Handwashing practice was assessed using 11 items based on the WHO Five Moments. Each correct practice (e.g., washing hands after touching a patient) was scored as "1" and an incorrect or omitted practice as "0". The total score was converted to a percentage. Based on adapted WHO criteria,^{5,14} overall practice was categorised as:

- **Good Practice:** Score of 67% or more (≥ 8 out of 11 items).
- **Fair Practice:** Score of 34% to 66% (4-7 items).
- **Poor Practice:** Score of 33% or less (≤ 3 items).

For bivariate and multivariable analysis, the outcome was dichotomised into "Good Practice" ($\geq 67\%$) vs. "Suboptimal Practice" ($\leq 66\%$). The Chi-square (χ^2) test was used to test associations between categorical independent variables and the dichotomised outcome. Variables with a p-value < 0.20 in bivariate analysis were entered into a multivariable logistic regression model to identify independent predictors of good handwashing practice. Adjusted odds ratios (aORs) with 95% confidence intervals (CIs) were calculated. A p-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval was obtained from the Health Research Ethics Committee of Ahmadu Bello University Teaching Hospital (Approval Number: ABUTHZ/HREC/B09/2018). Written informed consent was obtained from all participants after explaining the study's purpose, procedures, and their right to withdraw at any time without penalty. All data were anonymised and kept confidential, with access restricted to the research team.

Results

Socio-demographic Characteristics

Of the 80 questionnaires distributed, 74 were fully completed and returned, yielding a response rate of 92.5%. The socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Socio-demographic Characteristics of Medical Doctors (n=74)

Characteristic	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Sex		
Male	59	79.7
Female	15	20.3
Age Group (years)		
18-30	17	23.0
31-39	32	43.2
40-49	22	29.7
50-60	3	4.1
Marital Status		
Single	32	43.2
Married	42	56.8
Duration of Service (years)		
<5	23	31.1
5-10	22	29.7
11-15	24	32.4
>15	5	6.8
Speciality		
Physicians (Internal Medicine)	34	45.9
Surgeons (General Surgery)	40	54.1

The majority were male (79.7%), with a mean age of 36.1 ± 8.4 years (range: 27-58 years). The median duration of professional practice was 8.2 years (IQR: 4.0 - 13.2). Slightly over half (54.1%) were surgeons.

Handwashing Practices and Perceptions

Overall, 67.6% (n=50) of medical doctors demonstrated good handwashing practice, while 32.4% (n=24) had suboptimal practice (fair or poor). Sixty per cent (n=44) of respondents reported having received formal training on hand hygiene.

The materials used for handwashing varied: water and soap were the most commonly used (78.3% and 77.0%, respectively), while alcohol-based hand rubs were used by 66.2% of respondents. Regarding the timing of handwashing, compliance was highest for actions perceived as self-protective. Most doctors reported washing hands after touching a patient (89.2%) and immediately after exposure to body fluids (86.5%). In contrast, compliance was lower for actions primarily protecting the patient, such as washing hands before touching a patient (54.1%) and immediately before a clean/aseptic procedure (63.5%). A quarter (25.7%) reported washing hands on assumption of duty.

Figure 1: Handwashing Materials Used by Medical Doctors in ABUTH, Zaria

The major barriers to optimal handwashing, as perceived by respondents, are presented in Figure 3. The most frequently cited challenges were lack of running water (81.7%), lack of soap (60.8%), and high patient load (60.8%). Regarding perceptions, 59.5% (n=44) of respondents believed that HAIs are commonly encountered in ABUTH, Zaria.

Figure 2: Self-Reported Compliance with Hand Hygiene Indications (WHO Five Moments)

Key: OAD: On assumption of duty, ATP: After touching a patient. IAEBF: Immediately after exposure to body fluids. IBC/AP: Immediately before a clean/aseptic procedure, AEISP: After exposure to the immediate surroundings of the patient, ACD: At close of duty.

Figure 3: Perceived Barriers to Optimal Handwashing Practice by Medical Doctors at ABUTH Factors Associated with Handwashing Practice

Bivariate analysis showed no statistically significant association between handwashing practice and sex ($\chi^2=0.44$, $p=0.51$), age ($\chi^2=0.55$, $p=0.46$), or duration of service ($\chi^2=1.65$, $p=0.20$). However, a significant

association was found between speciality and handwashing practice, with surgeons demonstrating better practice than physicians ($\chi^2=4.82$, $p=0.028$).

Multivariable logistic regression analysis (Table 2) was performed to control for potential confounders. After adjustment, speciality remained the only significant predictor. Surgeons were 2.5 times more likely to have good handwashing practice compared to physicians (aOR = 2.51; 95% CI: 1.01 – 6.25; $p = 0.048$). While females had higher odds of good practice (aOR=1.94) and those with ≥ 10 years of service also had higher odds (aOR=1.73), these associations were not statistically significant. The wide confidence interval for the speciality association suggests some imprecision, likely due to the sample size.

Table 2: Multivariable Logistic Regression Analysis of Predictors of Good Handwashing Practice (n=74)

Characteristic	aOR	95%CI	p-value
Sex			
Male	1.00 (Ref)	0.48	
Female	1.94	7.86	0.353
Duration of Service (years)			
<10	1.00 (Ref)	0.64	
≥ 10	1.73	4.68	0.280
Speciality			
Physicians	1.00 (Ref)	1.01	
Surgeons	2.51	6.25	0.048

aOR = Adjusted Odds Ratio; CI = Confidence Interval; Ref = Reference category

Discussion

This study assessed handwashing practices and associated factors among medical doctors in a tertiary hospital in Northern Nigeria. The findings reveal that while a majority (67.6%) demonstrated good overall practice based on self-report, significant gaps remain, particularly in compliance with hand hygiene before patient contact and aseptic procedures. This level of self-reported practice is comparable to findings from a post-intervention study in Southeastern Nigeria (65.3%) but is higher than the 31% compliance observed in a direct observational study in another Northern Nigerian

tertiary hospital.^{10,15} The discrepancy between our findings and the lower observational rates underscores a critical limitation of self-reported data, which is prone to social desirability bias, where respondents may over-report compliant behaviour. This suggests that the true level of practice in ABUTH may be lower than 67.6%.

The pattern of hand hygiene compliance observed, with higher adherence after patient contact or exposure to body fluids and lower adherence before contact, is consistent with global literature.^{7,16} This "after" vs. "before" gap reflects a behavioural driver rooted in self-protection rather than a comprehensive understanding of infection transmission dynamics, which requires protecting patients from the HCW's own flora.⁵ This finding highlights a critical knowledge-to-action gap that educational interventions alone may not bridge. It necessitates a culture shift where patient safety is an equally strong motivator.

The significant association between speciality and handwashing practice, with surgeons being 2.5 times more likely to report good practice than physicians, is an important finding. This aligns with studies that have identified surgical disciplines as having a stronger culture of aseptic technique, reinforced by rigorous preoperative scrubbing protocols and a tangible consequence (surgical site infections).¹⁷ However, the borderline p-value and wide confidence interval around the aOR warrant cautious interpretation. While suggestive of a true effect, it may also be influenced by the relatively small sample size. The professional norms of surgery could be leveraged to promote a stronger hand hygiene culture hospital-wide, for example, by involving surgical leaders as champions for IPC.

The barriers identified in this study are overwhelmingly systemic and infrastructural, a hallmark of healthcare in many LMICs. The lack of running water and soap, reported by over 60% of respondents, represents a fundamental failure of the healthcare system to provide the bare necessities for safe care.^{3,18} This starkly contrasts with high-income countries, where the predominant barriers are often behavioural, such as forgetfulness or lack of time.⁷ Until these basic Water, Sanitation, and Hygiene (WASH) infrastructure deficits are addressed, even the most motivated and well-trained doctor will struggle to comply with hand hygiene standards. The high patient load further compounds this problem, as it increases the number of hand hygiene opportunities, making compliance even more challenging when facilities are inadequate.

While 60% of respondents reported receiving formal hand hygiene training, this did not translate into optimal practice for one-third of them. This reinforces the notion that training is necessary but not sufficient. Effective IPC requires a multi-modal strategy, as advocated by the WHO, which combines training with continuous system support (ensuring supplies), behavioural nudges (reminders, feedback), and a strong institutional safety climate with administrative backing and accountability.^{4,6,19}

A key strength of this study is its specific focus on medical doctors, an often-overlooked group in hand hygiene

research in Nigeria, despite their pivotal role in patient care and as role models. The use of a validated tool adapted from WHO guidelines strengthens the internal validity.

However, the findings must be interpreted in light of several limitations. First, the reliance on self-reported data is the most significant limitation, as it is highly susceptible to social desirability and recall bias, potentially inflating the reported compliance rates. Future studies should incorporate direct observation (e.g., using trained observers or automated monitoring systems) to obtain a more objective measure. Second, the cross-sectional design captures practice at a single point in time and cannot establish causality or assess the sustainability of practices. Third, the study was conducted in a single tertiary centre, which may limit the generalizability of findings to other hospitals, particularly secondary or primary care facilities with different resource levels. Finally, the relatively small sample size, while statistically justified, resulted in wide confidence intervals for some estimates, indicating a need for larger, multi-centre studies to confirm these findings.

Conclusion

This study highlights a significant gap between self-reported hand hygiene knowledge and actual practices among medical doctors in a Nigerian tertiary hospital. Although two-thirds claim good practices, deficiencies persist, especially in patient-protective moments, exacerbated by poor infrastructure. Surgeons exhibit better performance, indicating that professional culture can enhance compliance. To improve patient safety, a transition is needed from individual training to a systems-focused approach. This entails investments in reliable WASH infrastructure and consistent availability of alcohol-based hand rubs, alongside a multi-modal strategy emphasising regular audits and feedback to instil a culture of safety for both patients and healthcare workers against preventable infections.

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Declarations

- **Funding:** This research received no specific grant from any funding agency in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors.
- **Conflicts of Interest/Competing Interests:** The authors declare that they have no competing interests.
- **Ethics Approval:** This study was approved by the Health Research Ethics Committee of Ahmadu Bello University Teaching Hospital, Zaria (ABUTHZ/HREC/B09/2018).
- **Consent to Participate:** Written informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

- **Data Availability:** The datasets generated during and/or analysed during the current study are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

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